

Solar-powered single-and double-effect directly air-cooled LiBr–H₂O absorption prototype built as a single unit

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HIGHLIGHTS

- This work presents a novel solar cooling air-cooled absorption prototype for buildings.
- The solution (LiBr–H₂O) and the refrigerant (H₂O) are cooled directly by air.
- The cooling is produced from solar energy when operates in single-effect mode.
- If the demand is not met the prototype is able to operate in double-effect mode.

ABSTRACT

This work describes an installation in Madrid, Spain, designed to test a new solar-powered air-cooled absorption refrigeration system. This installation essentially consists of a 48 m² field of flat-plate solar collectors, a 1500-L hot water storage tank and a single and-double effect air-cooled lithium bromide absorption prototype. Designed and built by our research group, this prototype is able to operate either as a single-effect unit (4.5 kW) or as a double-effect unit (7 kW). In operation as single-effect mode, the prototype is driven by solar energy, whereas in operation as a double effect mode, an external energy source may be used. The prototype's evaporator is connected to a fan-coil placed inside an 80-m² laboratory that represent the average size of a Spanish housing unit. In August 2009, the cooling system was tested in the single-effect operation mode. The results show that the system is able to meet approximately 65% of the laboratory's seasonal cooling demand, although 100% may be reached for a few days. The prototype can also operate in double-effect mode to meet the cooling demand. In that case, the prototype is fed by thermal oil, which is warmed until it reaches the process temperature in the high-temperature generator. The prototype can operate in either single-effect mode or in double-effect mode or can also operate simultaneously both modes using the components common to both modes, namely, the absorber, evaporator, condenser, solution pumps and control equipment. This paper reports the experimental results from the prototype operating separately in single-effect and double-effect mode.

Keywords: Absorption, Lithium bromide, Direct air-cooled, Solar cooling, Single-double effect

1. Introduction

Building cooling is a relatively new and expanding market in both the residential and tertiary sectors of Spain, and the demand for air conditioning is growing rapidly all over the world, particularly in moderate climates. A subset of the main causes of this growth includes higher living standards, increasing requirements for comfort,

increases in the internal thermal loads of buildings due to improved computer equipment (specifically in the services sector), universally designed buildings that are not tailored to the local climate conditions, and a tendency towards higher outdoor temperatures.

A recent study on the cooling market reports that although a total residential use area of $20.9 \times 10^9 \text{ m}^2$ exists in Europe, only 5% of that area was air-conditioned at the beginning of this century [1]. However, the air-conditioning rate is 27% in the service sector, with $7.0 \times 10^9 \text{ m}^2$ available. This rate ranged between 70% and 100% in both the EEUU and Japan. Additionally, air conditioning equipment sales have multiplied in the last decades [2]. Therefore, the building cooling market in Europe is expected to accelerate vigorously. Reports state that the air conditioning rate reached 50% in dwellings [3] and 60% in the service sector in 2012, according to [1], these rates will entail an annual cooling demand of 660 TW h. Nevertheless, although this increase is occurring particularly rapidly in certain European countries, it is a worldwide trend. Therefore, a study was initiated by the Japan Refrigeration and Air-Conditioning Industry Association (JRAIA), which estimated that the annual number of air-conditioning equipment installations has shifted from 44.6 million in 2002 to 52.3 million in 2006. In addition, it is noteworthy that the main increase is taking place in the sale of small-power compact units (room air conditioner units or RAC). According to [4], although 26 million of these units were installed around the world in 1998, the forecast predicted 40 million units in 2006, equivalent to an installed electrical power of greater than 250 GW. However, the market for centralized cooling equipment seems to have remained stable [2,4].

The strong growth of the cooling market means a considerable increase in the electric demand, and the demand peaks on the hot- test days of the year are particularly critical [5]. This fact could compromise the stability of the electrical systems in many regions of the world and force large investments to strengthen this infrastructure. Furthermore, increasing CO_2 emissions could drive an increase in the consumption of fossil resources for electricity generation. Despite these observations, it is necessary to consider the significant global warning potential of the refrigerants used in conventional air-cooling machines. Although the use of fluorinated gases has been limited or forbidden, the inevitable leakage of refrigerant from the units currently in use poses a serious threat to the environment.

The unsustainability of the cooling market has led us to consider solar refrigeration as an alternative to conventional electric cooling machines. The maximum solar radiation coincides with the maximum cooling demand in a given day, which makes solar cooling systems quite suitable for replacement of the conventional units. Moreover, it is worth emphasizing that this technology commonly uses natural refrigerants, which are environmentally friendly. As a consequence, solar refrigeration is considered to be an ideal option for reducing fossil resource consumption, avoiding global warming emissions and increasing the stability of the electrical supply system.

In recent years, numerous research and demonstration projects have been developed for various solar cooling technologies suitable for buildings, as shown in [6–10]. From these studies, it was concluded that among the available alternatives, solar absorption cooling is the most attractive for substitution of traditional equipment. Readers interested can find an introduction to vapor absorption system in [11]. Currently, the only $\text{LiBr-H}_2\text{O}$ absorption machines for building air conditioning available on the market, which are single or double effect, are water-cooled. Therefore, these units require a cooling tower to cool the condenser and absorber, which necessitate high water consumption. This fact makes the cooling process costly and unsustainable because it consumes a scarce resource in regions with high cooling demands, such as Southern European and Mediterranean countries. In addition to increasing the cost of the installation, the need for cooling towers makes it difficult place these machines in buildings as a consequence of the increased size and the potential Legionella hazard.

As a consequence, air-cooled absorption machines appear to be the best choice for air conditioning of buildings, specifically in small-power-use situations. In recent years, numerous studies have been performed to overcome the main drawback of this technology, which is the risk of solution crystallization due to the high condenser and absorber operation temperatures [12,13]. Nevertheless, there is no suitable machine currently available in the market.

The only experimental results for a commercial air-cooled absorption machine come from a solar-driven single-effect unit commercialized by the Rotartica company [14].

However, solar-driven cooling systems are not usually designed to satisfy 100% of the seasonal cooling demand due to variability of the energy source, lack of space, more expensive installation, and other factors. Commonly, the solar fraction represents $2/3$ of the cooling seasonal demand [15]. The remaining third is produced with another air conditioning option, using a conventional system or feeding the generator of the absorption machine with the heat produced by combustion in a boiler. The first option entails an extra cooling system, with the subsequent drawbacks for the absorption system. The second option would be less costly if it were possible to use the same boiler for space heating. Nevertheless, neither of these options is energy-efficient because the first option involves use of electric energy to meet the cooling demand and the second option involves meeting the cooling demand by

burning fuel with an efficiency (COP) of approximately 0.6. This situation illustrates one of the main problems that prevent solar cooling from becoming competitive relative to the conventional mechanical compression cooling systems. Other obstacles that hamper the development of solar cooling systems are the absence of small-power units for commercial and residential use and systems that are large and costly due to the lack of design standardization and manufacturing of equipment [6–10,12].

This work presents a new refrigeration technology that could aid in overcoming a portion of the problems that create obstacles to the use of solar cooling in buildings. This work focuses on an air-cooled LiBr–H₂O absorption prototype able to operate in single-effect mode or in double-effect mode depending on solar energy availability. The designed unit and constructed prototype meet this requirement and have been evaluated experimentally. The prototype has a nominal cooling power of 4.5 kW operating in single-effect mode and 7 kW operating in double-effect mode. This work describes the installation setup for the experimental evaluation and reports the experimental results obtained in the summer of 2009 and 2010 in Madrid. During the experiments, the prototype operated in single-effect mode driven by thermal solar energy or in double-effect driven by thermal oil (although it also can be driven by burning fuel, as shown in [16]). The components common to both modes are the absorber, evaporator, condenser, solution pumps and control equipment [17].

2. System description

2.1. Air-cooled absorption cooling plant

Fig. 1 shows the installation diagram built by the Planta Experimental de Energía Solar owned by CSIC in Arganda del Rey (Madrid). The installation consists of three differentiated parts: heat production, cooling unit (prototype) and cooled water distribution installation.

Fig.1. Facility used to test the air-cooled single-and-double effect prototype.

When the prototype operates in single-effect mode, the low-temperature generator is driven by solar energy. If the amount of solar energy is not sufficient for the prototype to meet the cooling demand, the unit operates in double-effect mode. In that case, the high-temperature generator may be heated by direct flame from combustion of a fossil fuel [16], or in the present case, by thermal oil (see Figs. 1 and 2).

The cooling prototype is installed in the interior of a climatic chamber with plug-in panels that allows it to reach interior summer temperatures throughout the entire year. In Fig. 2, the chamber is closed.

The solar installation consists of three loops: the heat production loop (primary loop), the storage loop (secondary loop) and the cooling distribution loop (tertiary loop). Additionally, a final cooling consumption loop (laboratory loop) is also installed. The primary loop consists of a solar flat plate collector field with a 48-m² surface area (42 m² of useful surface area), a recirculation pump and the plate heat exchanger's hot side. The collector field directly faces the south with a tilt angle of 30°. The secondary loop consists of the plate heat exchanger's cold side, a thermal storage tank with a 1500-L capacity and a recirculation pump. The tertiary loop consists of the cooling machine and the pump that circulates the hot water from the storage tank to the single-effect generator, as shown in Fig. 2. The cool water produced in the evaporator circulates to the fan coil located inside the laboratory. Further information on the solar facility is given in Ref. (18).

The heat source for the prototype operating in double-effect mode consists of a group of electric resistances submerged in a tank of oil. The electric power consumption of the resistances (10 kW) heats the oil to 185 °C. A pump circulates the hot oil to the high-temperature generator of the double-effect prototype.

Fig. 2. Solar installation and single-double effect lithium-bromide air cooled prototype.

2.2. Conditioned room

The solar installation was designed to meet the cooling demand of a laboratory with 80-m² surface area, which simulates a common Spanish dwelling. The water distribution installation cooled by the prototype consists of a pump that circulates cool water to the laboratory and a fan-coil with a rated power of 10 kW connected to the air distribution ductwork to meet the laboratory thermal load. The maximum thermal load of the laboratory is approximately 8 kW when the outside temperature is 42 °C.

3. Single-double effect chiller prototype

To the best of the authors' knowledge, the first reference to a combination lithium-bromide single-double effect absorption chiller appeared in US Patent 4 439999 titled "Absorption Type Refrigeration System" (19). The patent protects a combination water-cooled single-double effect chiller in which the high-temperature double-effect chiller is powered by the heat released by internal combustion engine exhaust gases, and the single-effect generator is powered by the cooling heat from the same engine. The patent claims include the use of exhaust gas in the double-effect high-temperature generator, cooling engine heat from the engine in the single-effect generator and spray in the absorber.

The new single-double effect prototype developed by this research group was patented in the European Union (20), and features the following innovations:

- A flat-sheet adiabatic absorber able to operate in extreme outdoor temperatures (tested up to $t_{amb} = 44.5$ °C) at which the solution does not crystallize [15-17].
- Air-cooled (usable also for water-cooled systems) condensation. Specifically, the condensation temperature at $t_{amb} = 44.5$ °C was 54 °C, being the absolute pressure 0.15 bar.
- A system for direct absorber and condenser cooling.

When integrated into a solar cooling system, this combination single-double effect prototype is able to use the heat from the renewable source (or the exhaust heat from an internal or external turbine combustion engine) to power the single-effect generator. When the renewable or exhaust heat is depleted, the system operates in a manner similar to that of a direct-fired double-effect facility in which fuel is burned (with maximum efficiency) to supply heat to the high-temperature double-effect generator [16]. If the building demand is partially covered by renewable solar or biomass energy or waste heat, the single-double-effect systems can be used simultaneously to burn fossil fuel in the double-effect system and meet the building demand completely.

3.1. Description

Fig. 2 illustrates the single-double effect prototype, and Fig. 3 presents the accompanying flow chart. The prototype contains three operating modes: single-effect, double-effect and simultaneous mode. A series of valves enables the prototype to alternate between single- and double-effect operation. In single-effect operation, the valves VIS, VES and VDD1 are open, and the valves VDD, 1B and V2 GB remain closed. In double-effect mode, the valves VIS, VES and VDD1 are closed, and the valves 1B, V2 GB, VDD, VEB, VESA and VESB remain open. In simultaneous mode, the solution pump (SP) feeds all three generators. For the prototype operating in single-effect mode, the specific Li-Br solution loop is shown by a broken line in Fig. 3.

Fig.3. Flow chart for the air-cooled single-double effect prototype.

The following components are common to the three operation modes: the absorber (ASB), evaporator (EVA), condenser (CON), solution pump (SP), recirculation solution pump (RSP) and fan.

The nominal cooling capacities of the prototype are 4.5 kW in single-effect mode operation, 7 kW in double-effect mode and 11 kW if the single-and double-effect modes operate simultaneously.

The proposed prototype differs from those that currently exist in the market because the same unit includes both a single- and a double-effect generator, and both generators use the remainder of the components, i.e., absorber, condenser, pumps, etc. Fig. 2 shows that the design of this prototype is highly compact, with a volume of approximately 1 m³. The reduced volume is facilitated by the use of a new high efficiency absorber, and a flat fan sheet that is air cooled [12,16,17]. This absorber is easy to manufacture and maintain and avoids the use of additives to enhance the mass and heat transfer.

A theoretical model for the system presented is found in Ref. [21]

4. Prototype operating in single effect mode

Fig. 4 shows a schematic diagram of the prototype operating in single-effect mode. As previously mentioned, only the generator and the heat recovery exchanger are specific to the single-effect operating mode. The other components are common to both operating modes. Both the absorber and the condenser are directly air cooled by the flow of air that pumps the fan.

Fig. 4. Schematic diagram of the single-effect configuration

4.1. Measurement and control equipment

To evaluate the prototype operation under different conditions, sensors were installed throughout the prototype to measure the values of the main thermodynamic properties in the inlet and out- Jet of each component, as shown in Fig. 4. The directly measured magnitudes include temperatures collected via the Pt 100 sensors, mass flows measured via ultrasonic flow sensors, and pressures noted by pressure sensors. The temperature of the water circulating on the tertiary loop is also measured along the generator (t_{iwg} , t_{owg}) as well as the temperature of the solution in the generator (t_g , t_9), the heat recovery exchanger (t_7 , t_{10}) and the absorber (t_{22} , t_{23} , t_{24}). The temperature of the cooled water that circulates on the laboratory loop is also measured along the evaporator (t_{iwe} , t_{owe}) as well as the temperature of the condensed refrigerant t_2 . Finally, the temperature of the airflow at the outlet of the condenser t_{oca} is measured. Flow sensors measure the flow of externa fluids in the generator (m_{wg}) and evaporator (m_{we}) as well as the solution flows in the absorber (m_s) and in the cooler (m_{sac}). The pressure is measured in the assembly absorber-evaporator (pd) and in the condenser (PH).

The measurement and control equipment for the solar installation consists of the following sensors (Fig. 1): temperature sensors in the inlet and outlet of the solar collector field (t_{iwc} , t_{owc}), temperature sensors in the inlet and outlet of the storage tank in the secondary loop (t_{iwt} , t_{owt}), and ultrasonic flow sensors to measure the flow in the primary (m_p) and secondary loops (m_s). A meteorological station measures the solar radiation (R), dry-bulb outdoor temperature (t_{amb}) and wind velocity (v). In addition, the indoor laboratory temperature and the airflow temperature at the fan coil outlet (t_{ofc}) are measured. All acquired data are processed via a data acquisition system (type DC-100).

4.2. Experimental results

This single-and double-effect absorption prototype was evaluated experimentally in 2009 and 2010 at the Planta Experimental de Energía Solar owed by CSIC in Arganda del Rey (Madrid). The experimental results of the prototype operating in single-effect mode and powered with solar energy on August 26, 28 and 29 and September 3 and 4 in 2009 are presented below. The daily results from August 28 are first presented in detail. Next, the overall results for the entire testing period are presented.

4.2.1. Experimental results on 28 August 2009

4.2.1.1. Environmental conditions. Fig. 5a and b shows the environmental conditions on 28 August 2009, namely, the outdoor dry bulb temperature, wind velocity and solar radiation. These values represent a typical summer day in Madrid, with high solar radiation and a maximum outdoor temperature of 36.5 °C. At night, the minimum outdoor temperature is near 19 °C. Fig. 5b shows the solar radiation on the horizontal plane and on the collector plane. The total daily energy incident on the solar collector field is 7.50 kWh.

Fig. 5. Environmental conditions on 28/08/2009: (a) Outdoor temperature and wind velocity and (b) solar radiation.

4.2.1.2. *Solar installation results.* Fig. 6a and b shows the operating variables of the solar installation. Fig. 6a shows the inlet and outlet temperatures of the collector field (primary loop, t_{iwo} , t_{owc}) and those of the storage tank (secondary loop, t_{iwc} , t_{owc}). Fig. 6b shows the mass flow rate of the primary and secondary loop.

Fig. 6b shows that the mass flow rates of the primary and secondary loop are 0.43 kg/s and 0.35 kg/s, respectively. When the installation stabilizes, the water flow circulating in the primary loop experiences a temperature increase of 9 °C, reaching a maximum temperature at the solar collector outlet of 113 °C between 13:00 and 14:00 h. The temperature difference between the inlet and outlet in the secondary loop lies between 7 °C and 8 °C for nearly the entire operation period. Nevertheless, starting from 13:00, this temperature difference begins to decline because the water temperature in the storage tank increases. Both figures show that the circulation pump of the primary loop operates intermittently starting from 14:25. As a result, temperature peaks occur as a consequence of the control strategy, which stops the secondary pump when the temperature difference between the primary and secondary loop reaches a certain set-point.

Fig. 6. Variables for the solar installation: Temperature (a) and mass flow rate (b) at the storage tank inlet and outlet in the secondary and tertiary loops.

Fig. 7a shows the incident solar power on the collector plane and the thermal power that the secondary loop delivers to the storage tank. The ratio of both magnitudes defines the efficiency of the solar installation, as shown in Fig. 7b. This figure also shows the efficiency of the solar collector field, which is computed as the ratio of the thermal energy collected by the primary circuit and the total solar radiation incident on the collector plane. An average daily balance shows that the total solar radiation incident on the collector plane is 303.74 kW h, and the thermal energy delivered to the tank is 65.42 kW h. Consequently, the efficiency of the solar collectors at 12:00 h is 0.34. Furthermore, the daily average efficiency of the solar installation is 0.22.

Fig. 7. Performance of the solar installation. (a) Solar radiation and heat power transferred to the storage tank. (b) Efficiency of the solar collector field and that of the solar installation.

4.22. Prototype results

Temperatures. The daily evolution of the solution temperature is reported in this section. Fig. 8a shows the inlet and outlet temperature in the generator for both the solution (t_8 , t_9) and the hot water circulating in the tertiary loop (t_{iwg} , t_{owg}). During prototype operation from approximately 9:30 to 16:00, hot water enters the generator at a temperature ranging from 90 °C to 106 °C and leaves the generator at temperatures approximately 5 °C colder. The solution, which boils between 80 °C and 95 °C, is heated in the generator up to approximately 13 °C. Fig. 8b shows the inlet and outlet solution temperature in the absorber (t_{11} , t_5) and the temperature at which the solution returns to the absorber from the absorber cooler (t_{24}). The cooling airflow inlet temperature (t_{amb}) is also shown for comparison. The figure does not show the solution temperatures t_{22} or t_{23} because both are similar to t_{11} . The absorber cooler is able to cool the solution to between 3 °C and 5 °C, thus preventing the solution from exceeding 45 °C. In other words, the absorber cooler keeps the solution temperature 4–7 °C higher than the outdoor temperature (t_{amb}).

Fig. 9a shows the refrigerant temperature in the condenser (t_2) in addition to the cooling airflow temperature after passing through the absorber (t_{amb}) and the condenser (t_{oca}). Similar to Figs. 8a, Fig. 9a shows the cooling airflow inlet temperature. The experimental results show that the air-cooling system is able to maintain the condensation temperature between 35 °C and 45 °C or approximately 8–9 °C above the ambient temperature, which highlights the good design. A comparison of the condensation temperature (t_2) with the absorption temperature (t_5) shows that t_2 stays within a maximum of 2–3 °C higher than t_5 .

Fig. 9b illustrates cool water production for air conditioning purposes, showing the inlet and outlet temperature of the chilled water in the evaporator (t_{iwe} , t_{owe}), the airflow temperature at the fan coil outlet (t_{ofc}) and the temperature inside the laboratory (t_{in}). The experimental results reveal that the prototype is able to maintain the laboratory temperature close to 25 °C, as established in the air-conditioning Spanish legislation [22]. This process involves cooling the air from 25 °C to approximately 16 °C even when the ambient temperature is 36.5 °C and the results show that the prototype is able to cool the water approximately 4 °C even under the most difficult conditions.

Fig. 8. Inlet and outlet solution temperatures: (a) generator and (b) absorber.

Fig. 9. (a) Condenser temperatures. (b) Chilled water temperatures. Laboratory temperature.

4.2.2.2. *Mass flow rates. Thermal powers and efficiency.* Fig. 10 shows the mass flow rates of several flows that take place in the prototype operation, namely, the generator and cooler absorber solution flows (m_s , m_{ac}) and the generator and evaporator water flows (m_{wg} , m_{we}). The water mass flow rates in the generator and in the evaporator are maintained at 0.29 kg/s and 0.27 kg/s, respectively. The solution mass flow rate in the absorber cooler oscillates near an average value of 0.53 kg/s, and these oscillations are due to the irregular pump operation. The solution mass flow rate in the generator is gradually increased during the test to increase the vapor refrigerant production and therefore the cooling power as well. The cooling airflow rate (absorber + condenser) is approximately 2.5 m³/s. The test began with a solution flow rate of approximately 0.025 kg/s, which reached a maximum of 0.055 kg/s when t_8 peaked. Thus, the chilled water temperature was maintained near 16 °C. The values of the various thermal powers involved in the prototype operation have been computed from the measured values of the mass flow rates and temperatures. Fig. 11a shows the thermal power supplied to the generator Q_g and rejected to the surroundings by the condenser-absorber assembly Q_{ca} in addition to the cooling power produced in the evaporator Q_e . The thermal power supplied by circulating hot water in the tertiary loop is 5 kW at the beginning of the test and stabilizes near 6.5 kW over four hours in the middle of the test. The cooling power is approximately 2–3 kW at the beginning of the test but reaches 4 kW at 12:00. During the peak cooling

demand hours, the prototype produced a cooling power of 4.5 kW in a sustained manner. The daily balance shows that the thermal energy supplied to the generator is 41.4 kW h and that rejected to the surroundings by the prototype air cooling operation is 68.8 kW h. The cooling energy produced in the evaporator is 25.4 kW h.

Fig. 10. Mass flow rates.

The total electricity power consumed by the ancillary equipment was about 0.60 kW: 0.40 kW the fan; 0.15 kW the recirculation solution pump (BRD) and 0.05 kW the generator solution pump (BD), Fig. 3. Accordingly, the electric COP is about 7.5. It should be noted that the electric COP of the absorption chiller model Rotartica 0.45v is about 5 [14].

The ratio between the evaporator and the generator power is referred to as the prototype thermal coefficient of performance or COP. Similarly, the ratio between the evaporator cooling power and the solar power incident on the solar collector field is known as the solar coefficient of performance or SCOP. Fig. 11a shows the values of the COP and SCOP in the test. The daily average values of the COP and the SCOP are 0.61 and 0.084, respectively, and the solar fraction reached 66% that day.

Fig. 11. (a) Heat power corresponding to the generator, evaporator and air-cooling system. (b) COP and SCOP.

4.3.3. Overall experimental results in the five-day tested period

This section reports the summarized results for the five days over which the prototype was tested during operation in single-effect mode. Fig. 12a presents the overall energy balance in this period and shows that the incident solar energy reached a similar value each day, ranging between 304 kW h/day and 309 kW h/day. The day on which incident solar energy reached its lowest value was 28 August 2009; this date was also the day on which the thermal energy transferred to the storage tank was the highest, although the difference is small. The thermal energy supplied to the generator is nearly constant, approximately 41 kW h/day. The cooling energy generated in the evaporator is 22.4 kW h/day on average, reaching a maximum value of 25.4 kW h/day on 28 August 2009.

Fig. 12b displays the daily efficiency of the solar installation and the daily values of the COP and SCOP. The daily value of the thermal COP ranges between 0.46 and 0.63, with an average value of 0.54 during the test period. Additionally, the figure shows that the daily value of the SCOP ranges between 0.6 and 0.08. Finally, the average solar fraction was 65%.

Fig.12. (a) Overall energy balance and (b) daily efficiencies and COP.

5. Prototype operating in double-effect mode

Fig. 13 shows a schematic diagram of the prototype operating in double-effect mode. Like in the single-effect mode, both the absorber and the condenser are directly air-cooled by the flow of air that pumps the fan. Note that both the absorber and the condenser are shared by the single-effect and the double-effect modes.

5.1. Measurement and control equipment

Similar to the single-effect mode, the values of the main thermodynamic properties were measured at the inlet and outlet of each component. Therefore, we measured the temperature of the oil flow ($t_{i,oil}$, $t_{o,oil}$) and that of the solution flow (t_{13} , t_{14}) in the high temperature generator as well as the temperature of the generated vapor water flow (t_{1A} , t_{1B}) and that of the solution flow (t_{18} , t_{19}) in the low temperature generator. We also measured the temperature of the solution flow in the heat recovery exchangers (t_{19} , t_{20} , t_{14} , t_{15}) and in the absorber (t_{25} , t_{26}). Additionally, we measured the temperature of the refrigerant flow in the evaporator (t_{iwe} , t_{owe}) and the outlet cooling airflow (t_{oca}). Finally, the temperature of the condensed refrigerant was measured (t_2). The flow sensors measure the oil flow in the high temperature generator (m_{oil}), in the evaporator (m_{we}) and in the solution flows ($m_{s,LG}$, $m_{s,HG}$, m_{sac}). The pressure was measured in the assembly absorber-evaporator (p_d) and in the condenser (P_H). In addition, the laboratory indoor temperature and the airflow temperature at the fan coil outlet (t_{ofc}) were measured. All acquired data were processed in a data acquisition system (type DC-100).

Fig. 13. Schematic diagram of the double-effect configuration.

5.2. Experimental results

The experimental results for the prototype operating in double-effect mode and powered with thermal oil during the days of August 18 and 25, 2010, and October 11, 2010, are presented below. The daily results from October 11, 2010, are first presented in detail, and the overall results for the entire tested period are subsequently presented.

5.2.1. Daily experimental results on 11 October 2010

5.2.1.1. Environmental conditions. As previously mentioned, the prototype is located inside a climatic chamber, as shown in Fig. 2. Therefore, it is possible to control the temperature of the surroundings. In summer, the prototype was operated with the chamber open, but the chamber remains closed during the remainder of the year.

The test began at 9:39 and ended at 17:00. Fig. 14 shows the temperature of the surrounding air inside the climatic chamber. The maximum and minimum temperature values were 35.8 °C and 26 °C, respectively.

Fig. 14. Temperature in the climatic chamber.

5.3. Prototype results

5.3.1. Temperatures

Fig. 15a shows the temperatures in the high temperature generator ($t_{i,oil}$, $t_{o,oil}$) and (t_{13} , t_{14}). The thermal oil is heated from 130 °C to 180 °C due to the heat produced by the electric resistance battery and is pumped to the generator that supplies thermal power to the solution. The supplied thermal power is quite low at the prototype start time, near 09:45 h, but steadily rises until it reaches its maximum value near 15:00. Consequently, the temperature difference between the oil and solution flows steadily increases from a low value of 6.1 °C near 15:00 h. At 15:45 h, the oil flow inlet and outlet generator temperatures are 179.6 °C and 175.1 °C, respectively.

The value of t_{14} is slightly less than that of $t_{i,oil}$ as a consequence of the design of the plate heat exchanger in the generator. Thus, at 14:00, $t_{i,oil}$ is 173.6 °C and t_{14} is 171.6 °C. The solution temperature of the generator inlet stemming from the high temperature heat recovery exchanger is 161 °C, which is increased by 10 °C until it boils. The electric resistance battery is disconnected at 15:95 h, and the temperature in the generator declines to 130 °C at 16:48 h.

Fig. 15b shows that the solution temperature at the low temperature generator inlet t_{18} ranges between 40 °C and 60 °C in the time interval between 11:30 and 16:00 h. The temperature of the refrigerant vapor flow from the high temperature generator t_{1A} ranges from 130 °C at the beginning of the test to 175 °C when the test is halted near 16:30. The vapor flow leaves the generator as reheated vapor and subsequently condenses to release its latent heat to the solution from the low temperature heat recovery exchanger. The vapor saturation temperature t_{1C} is approximately 100 °C (1.0 bar saturation pressure) at 09:30 and steadily rises until reaching a maximum temperature of 113 °C (1.6 bar saturation pressure) at 16:30 h.

The solution temperature at the flow temperature generator outlet t_{19} ranges between 79.6 °C at 10:00h and 92.8 °C at 16:00 and subsequently declines.

Fig. 15. Temperature in the generators: (a) high-temperature generator and (b) low-temperature generator.

Fig. 16a and b shows the temperature decrease that experiences the concentrated solution flow that circulates to the absorber in both the high and low temperature heat recovery exchanger. In the high temperature recovery heat exchanger, the solution that comes to the high temperature generator is cooled down about 20 °C at 11:00 and about 25 °C at 15:00. In the low temperature recovery heat exchanger, the temperature of the solution that comes to the low temperature generator is decreased a value that ranges between 120 °C and 170 °C.

Fig. 16. Temperature decrease in the solution flow that circulates to the absorber, showing the heat recovery exchanger effectiveness: (a) high-temperature heat recovery exchanger and (b) low-temperature heat recovery exchanger.

Figures also show the effectiveness of both heat recovery exchangers. This ranges between 0.85 and 0.9 in the high temperature heat recovery exchanger and between 0.55 and 0.60 in the low temperature heat recovery exchanger.

Fig. 17a shows the most relevant solution temperatures in the absorber, namely, the absorber outlet temperature (t_5) and the temperature of the air-cooled solution returned to the absorber from the absorber cooler (t_{25}). The temperature difference between the two is 6 °C at 11:00, increasing to near 10 °C at 15:00 h. The solution delivered from the absorber cooler, which is cool and diluted in refrigerant, mixes with the concentrated solution from the high- and low-temperature generators and leaves the absorber to flow to the absorber cooler and the heat recovery exchangers. The value of t_{25} is approximately 6 °C higher than the temperature of the surroundings (t_{amb}).

Fig. 17b shows the inlet and outlet temperature of the airflow that directly cools the absorber-condenser assembly (t_{amb} , t_{oca}). As shown in Fig. 13, the airflow pumped by the fan cools the absorber solution, condenses the refrigerant vapor that circulates in the condenser and cools the hot water condensed in the low-temperature generator. The maximum temperature increases experienced by the cooling airflow are close to 7 °C, leaving the condenser at approximately 43 °C. The cooling airflow rate is approximately 2.5 m³/s. The refrigerant condensation temperature (t_2) is approximately 11 °C higher than the surrounding temperature (t_{amb}).

Fig. 17. (a) Temperature in the absorber and (b) airflow temperature in the absorber cooler.

5.3.2. Powers and efficiency

Fig. 18a shows the thermal power supplied to the high temperature generator Q_{HG} and the cooling power produced in the evaporator Q_e . The value reached by both powers is close to 4.5 kW for most of the test. Fig. 18b presents the thermal coefficient of operation performance (COP) and reveals that the COP is approximately 1.0 for most of the test and its diary value is near 1.0.

Fig. 18. (a) Thermal power in the high temperature generator and in the evaporator. (b) Thermal coefficient of operation performance.

5.4. Conditioning equipment

Fig. 19 shows the most relevant temperatures in the laboratory, namely, the inlet and outlet chilled water temperature (t_{iwe} , t_{owe}) and the laboratory inside temperature (t_{in}). As previously mentioned, the weather conditions on 11 October 2010 were different than those on a hot summer day. Thus, a battery of electric resistances of 8 kW installed in the fan-coil, was used to create the temperature inside the laboratory that would simulate a hot summer day.

The average temperature inside the laboratory was maintained at 25 °C during the test with the electric resistance battery running. The figure shows that the average chilled water inlet and outlet temperatures are 13.5 °C and 18 °C, being the evaporation pressure 11.5 mbar and 16 mbar, respectively. The chilled water that leaves the laboratory returns to the evaporator where it is cooled again. The oscillations in the inside temperature are due to the battery's electric resistance control system. Eventually, the cooling production was able to meet the demand for this day.

Fig. 19. Temperatures in the laboratory.

5.5. Overall experimental results in the three-day tested period

Fig. 20 shows the overall experimental results from the three days, 18 and 25 August and 11 October 2010, in which the prototype was tested while operating in double-effect mode. Specifically, the figure shows the daily energy balance in the generator and the evaporator as well as the daily thermal COP.

It is observed that the daily energy supplied to the generator on 11 October 2010 was approximately 28 kW h/day, which was clearly higher than that of the other two days. Additionally, the daily cooling energy production was clearly higher as well, near 27 kW h/day. However, the COP reached a value slightly lower than 1, whereas the COP was greater than 1.02 on the two other days. These results occurred despite the observation that on October 11, 2010, the temperature in the climatic chamber was slightly lower (3 °C) and the temperature of the high temperature generator was 180 °C, or 10 °C higher than on the other two days.

Fig. 20. Overall energy balance.

6. Uncertainty analysis

In this section, uncertainty is analysed and summarized according to Marcos [23]. The data acquisition equipment used in this work consisted of PT100 thermo resistances, pressure transducers and mass flow meters, whose accuracy were respectively 0.1 K, 0.25% and 1-3%. Besides, a DC-100 acquisition system registered all the measurements with an accuracy of 0.05%. Taking into account error propagation, uncertainty in calculated parameters is the following: 8.1% for cooling power, 6.1% for heating capacity and 9.5% for COP.

7. Conclusions

This work presents a novel lithium bromide absorption prototype, directly air-cooled, powered by solar thermal energy, which can operate dually: single or double-effect mode, working as a single unit. Additionally, both operation modes share the same air-cooled absorber-condensation subsystem. The cooling energy is produced from thermal solar energy when the prototype operates in single-effect mode. For the case in which the cooling demand is not met, the prototype is able to operate in double-effect mode. The following conclusions are presented:

- (a) Prototype operating in single-effect mode.

Experimental results are shown for the prototype and for the solar installation that powered it during a five-day period in summer 2009.

The daily efficiency of the solar installation is 0.20, and the daily thermal coefficient of performance of the prototype is 0.54, reaching a maximum value of 0.63. Additionally, the maximum cooling power was 4.5 kW, producing chilled water at 16 °C when the outdoor temperature was 36 °C. These results show that both the solar

installation and the prototype operated efficiently.

Comparing the results achieved by the prototype with those of the only machine, but using the re-cooling system, on the market with similar characteristics (Rotartica 045v) [14], it is concluded that the prototype operated with higher efficiency, although this design has not yet been optimized. Thus, under similar conditions of outdoor temperature and solar radiation, the prototype is able to produce chilled water nearly 2 °C lower and with a COP slightly higher than those of the Rotartica machine, but since the electric COP is higher about 7.5, the electricity consumption is lower.

(b) Prototype operating in double-effect mode.

Experimental results are shown for the prototype operation on October 11, 2010. On this day, the surrounding temperature for the prototype and the temperature inside the laboratory were artificially created to simulate a summer hot day.

The experimental results show that with an exterior dry bulb temperature of 35.5 °C. the maximum temperatures of absorption and condensation were 41.5 °C and 46 °C, respectively, being the chilled water temperature about 12 °C. The maximum boiling temperature in the high temperature generator was 175 °C. Additionally, the efficiencies of the high- and low-temperature heat recovery exchangers were near 0.9 and less than 0.6, respectively. This result encourages us to improve the design of this heat recovery system, which could result in an increase in the thermal coefficient of operation for this operation mode.

The results show that the cooling power was similar to that of the single-effect mode, but the thermal coefficient of operation was doubled versus that of the single-effect mode.

(c) Common components.

The common components of both operation modes (i.e., the absorber, condenser, cooler absorber, solution and recirculation pumps and fan) operated efficiently in both modes.

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Appendix A. Uncertainty analysis

According to Kline [24], the uncertainty of the experimental result $P(x_1, x_N)$ has been estimated from the uncertainties of the measured variables x_1, x_N according to the following expression

$$\delta P = \left[\left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_1} \delta x_1 \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_2} \delta x_2 \right)^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_N} \delta x_N \right)^2 \right]^{1/2}$$

where δP refers to the uncertainty of the result and $\delta x_1, \dots, \delta x_N$ are the uncertainties of the measured variables.

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